

Deliverable D8.11

Data Management Plan – preliminary (M6)

WP 8

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Project Summary

The strategic objective of CityCLIM is to significantly contribute to delivering the next-generation of City Climate Services based on advanced weather forecast models enhanced with data both from existing, but insufficiently used, sources and emerging data sources, such as satellite data (e.g., Copernicus data) or data generated by Citizens Science approaches for Urban Climate Monitoring etc. For City Climate Services, data products of interest related to land surface properties, atmospheric properties (e.g., aerosol optical thickness), geometry etc. For all of those, information of interest concerns e.g., Copernicus data products and services that are already existing (e.g., based on Sentinel-3/OLCI, PROBA-V, SPOT, Sentinel-1, MetopASCAT data), will exist in the near future (based on already flying satellites such as Sentinel-2), or will exist in the mid-term (based on satellites currently under development) and long-term (based on satellites soon starting concept phase) future. The project will establish; (i) an open platform allowing for efficient building of services based on access to diverse data; (ii) enhanced weather models based on data from diverse existing and emerging sources; (iii) a set of City Climate Services customizable to specific needs of users in cities; and (iv) a generic Framework for building next generation of Urban Climate Services. CityCLIM will be driven by 4 Pilots addressing diverse climate regions in Europe (Luxembourg, Thessaloniki, Valencia, Karlsruhe) which will define requirements upon the tools to be developed, support specification and testing of the services and serve as demonstrators of the selected approaches and the developed technologies. The Consortium will elaborate business plan to assure sustainability of the platform and services.

Project Consortium

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Document Summary

The Deliverable D8.11-Data Management Plan contains preliminary information about the data, the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved. The DMP describes the standard formats, meaningful Metadata, and open repositories to share data and enable other users to build on the knowledge gained during the project.

This deliverable also outlines how the research data collection or generation will be handled during and after the CityCLIM project, describes which data collection and generation methodology will be followed and whether and how data will be shared. It defines and establishes consistent practices among project partners to increase the efficiency and robustness of data handling during the project. The project will manage data in accordance with the principles of FAIR data management (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable data) and this deliverable explains what information are needed to fulfil this tasks.

The proposed work in CityCLIM will fully comply with the regulations set out in the GDPR. In addition, CityCLIM comply with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out (EC 2005, ALLEA 2017). Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research. The ethical aspects impacting the CityCLIM project are described in detail in Ethics Requirements deliverable and responds to the findings of the ethics review performed by the European Commission in the proposal evaluation phase. However, since the ethic deliverables are confidential documents, a summary of the ethics and privacy strategy is included in this document.

This D8.11 represents an initial version of the DMP, prepared during the first six months of the project lifetime. Obviously, the DMP will be updated regularly during the project lifetime since not all data or potential uses are well defined at this stage.

Abbreviations

App	Software Application
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of the Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
e.g.	Exempli gratia = for example
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
i.e.	id est = that is to say
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
RTD	Research and Technological Development
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	7
1.1	Content and Purpose.....	7
2	Building a data management plan in the context of H2020.....	8
2.1	Purpose of the CityCLIM Data Management Plan	8
2.1.1	Requirements for Research Data	8
2.1.2	DMP value	8
2.2	Legal Framework	9
3	Data Management Plan Overview	10
3.1	CityCLIM Data Management Procedure	10
3.2	Who will be responsible for data management in the project?	10
3.2.1	Definition of Roles	11
4	Data Summary	13
4.1	Data summary at a primary state	13
4.2	Naming Convention	14
4.3	Versioning.....	15
4.4	Metadata provision	16
4.5	Data Handling and Management at a primary stage.....	16
4.6	Data Management Plan using OpenAIRE	17
4.7	Data Repository	17
5	General Provisions - FAIR Data Management	18
6	Data generated in the CityCLIM Project	18
7	Ethics	19
7.1	Ethical Issues.....	19
7.2	European and national regulations.....	19
7.3	Ethical Measures in CityCLIM project	21
8	Overview of Datasets	23
9	References.....	34

List of Figures

Figure 1:	CityCLIM Data Management Procedure.	10
Figure 2:	Required metadata information.	16
Figure 3:	Data (green box) in the CityCLIM project according to proposal.	18

List of Tables

Table 1:	Tasks of responsible persons regarding data management in the CityCLIM project.....	11
Table 2:	Points and questions and their explanation regarding data summary.	13
Table 3:	Proposed CityCLIM naming convention.	15
Table 4:	Information on datasets at a primary stage.	16
Table 5:	Regulations in the partner countries (DLA Piper Intelligence (2022)).....	20
Table 6:	Examples of data generated within CityCLIM	23
Table 7:	Example 1- WP2.....	24
Table 8:	Example 2- WP3.....	25
Table 9:	Example 3- WP3.....	26
Table 10:	Example 4- WP4.....	27
Table 11:	Example 5- WP5.....	28
Table 12:	Example 6- WP6.....	29
Table 13:	Example 7- WP6.....	30
Table 14:	Example 8- Pilot Region Karlsruhe.	31
Table 15:	Example 9- Pilot Region Karlsruhe	32
Table 16:	Example 10- Pilot Region Valencia.	33

1 Introduction

1.1 Content and Purpose

The Deliverable D8.11-Data Management Plan contains preliminary information about the data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved. The purpose of the Data Management Plan is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that the Consortium will use concerning all the datasets that the project will generate. The DMP describes the standard formats, meaningful Metadata, and open repositories to share data and enable other users to build on the knowledge gained during the project. The first audience to which this report is addressed is the internal partners; there are thirteen partner organizations from Germany, Greece, Spain, Switzerland, Austria and Luxembourg.

This deliverable also outlines how the research data collection or generation will be handled during and after the CityCLIM project, describes which data collection and generation methodology will be followed and whether and how data will be shared.

Firstly, the DMP defines and establishes consistent practices among project partners to increase the efficiency and robustness of data handling during the project. The second audience of this report is the community of researchers, engineers, and biofuel producers interested in the data and the tools of the CityCLIM.

This report represents an initial version of the DMP, prepared during the first six months of the project lifetime. Obviously, the DMP will be updated regularly during the project lifetime since not all data or potential uses are well defined at this stage. New versions of the DMP will be created whenever significant changes occur in the project due to new data sets, modifications in consortium policies or other external factors. A final version (D8.12) will be released in month 36, which will be public again. The DMP will be continuously updated until the end of the project. Open access (OA) refers to the free provision of scientific information (data, findings, publications, etc.) to others through online means. In the question, why make my research open access?; the justification lies on economic and ethical principles as:

- the undertaken research has been paid with public funds and
- there is no reason to pay again to gain access to this information when it is required for use by other researchers, industries, students, or citizens.

According to the "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020" (EC 2017), it is encouraged to provide open access to scientific publications and data, as this contributes to:

- i) the quality improvement of research by building on a more substantial body of existing work,
- ii) increase in efficiency of research by reducing duplication of effort,
- iii) innovations to market quicker by reducing barriers to information flow,
- iv) enhancement of the transparency of scientific progress.

The first step after each research is to decide how to disseminate its results. The two options are either to publish the research findings or to keep confidential some aspects for commercial exploitation.

The CitiCLIM Management Plan (D8.11), led by UFZ to be delivered in M6 (March 2022), will outline the main processes that determine the path for different aspects of the project.

2 Building a data management plan in the context of H2020

2.1 Purpose of the CityCLIM Data Management Plan

The purpose of the preliminary Data Management Plan (DMP) for the CityCLIM project is to put in place the details and definitions that will facilitate the potential reuse of the data collected and processed within the project. The DMP will ensure that this data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot. An updated version of the DMP will be released if other kinds of data will be generated/collected, if changes in consortium policies or consortium composition occur, and if any other external factors affect the validity of the present DMP.

2.1.1 Requirements for Research Data

A new element in Horizon 2020 is using Data Management Plans (DMPs) detailing what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved. A Data Management Plan is required for projects participating in the Open Research Data Pilot.

The requirements of the participating projects regarding research data are listed in the following. The participating projects should, according to OpenAire (2022):

- manage all research publications, data, and other outputs following the FAIR principles
- make research data openly accessible immediately (make data accessible at the latest within 30 days of generation) and in line with the FAIR principles
- develop provisions for access to the data if open access is not possible because of exceptions as described in GA Article 29.3; principle "As open as possible, as closed as necessary."
- deposit quality-controlled research data in a data repository as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the data management plan (DMP) ensures persistent and unique identifiers (PIDs) usages, keep in focus sustainability, Metadata, curation and quality assurance, access (e.g., free and easy access to reuse), security, privacy, common format, provenance (e.g., maintains a detailed log file of changes to datasets and metadata)
- provide essential information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to reuse or validate the data
- include metadata of deposited data under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0 1.0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable)

As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), a DMP should address the following essential aspects (OpenAire 2022):

- a description of the data generated/collected, including data types and an estimate of its size within the project.
- whether and how the data will be made accessible for verification and reuse, along with relevant security and privacy considerations.
- how the research data will be managed (organized, curated, accessed, shared, preserved)
- timelines of when generated data will be made open access.
- an estimation of curation and storage/preservation costs; person/team responsible for data management and quality assurance processes

2.1.2 DMP value

Data Management Plans are an essential mechanism for research groups to ensure their outputs are FAIR and ensure that data management becomes a core part of all research practice (EC 2018). The added value of a DMP can be summarized in the following points:

- To understand how to reuse and exploit data
- To increase the quality of research by defining institutional and project-specific data management policies and plans in accordance with relevant standards and community best practice
- To ensure that all research outputs are findable for everyone/available to people by using persistent identifier

- To understand strength and weaknesses (e.g. what discipline/ unit produces more results? Are data described based on DMP requirements? etc.
- To ensure research integrity and excellence of researchers

2.2 Legal Framework

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, since May 2018) is applicable in all EU Member States and the countries in the European Economic Area (EEA) to strengthen citizens' fundamental rights and guarantee their privacy in the digital age (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016, on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC).

The individual rights include the right to (EC 2022):

- Obtain information about the processing of personal data
- Obtain access to the personal data held about one person
- Ask for correction of incorrect, inaccurate, or incomplete personal data
- Request that personal data be erased when it is no longer needed or if processing it is unlawful;
- Object to the processing of personal data for marketing purposes or on grounds relating to a particular situation
- Request the restriction of the processing of personal data in specific cases;
- Receive personal data in a machine-readable format and send it to another controller ("data portability") and
- Request that decisions based on automated processing concerning one person or significantly affecting this person and based on this personal data are made by natural persons, not only by computers. In this case, there is the right to express the personal point of view and to contest the decision.

3 Data Management Plan Overview

3.1 CityCLIM Data Management Procedure

Figure 1 illustrates the Data Management Procedure. In the CityCLIM project, various data will be produced, used, or derived from satellite, airborne and historical data. Satellite data are accessed mainly by existing open-access hubs, e.g., Copernicus (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>). Copernicus provides complete, free and open access to different Sentinel products. If these products are processed, e.g., in a different format, the information should be included in the DMP. Airborne data include airborne sensors and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV): LST and LSE maps from the brightness temperature data. Apart from this, measured data include in-situ data or data collected from citizen science (e.g., subjective perception of heat). Historical weather and model data will be used to assess the temporal variation in specific parameters to be included in forecast models or specific CityCLIM engines. A significant part of the data generated in the project is model data. Following exemplarily models are used in the project: ultra HD Weather Model Processor with the inclusion of CAMS model aerosol, Urban Heat Forecast Engine with the inclusion of soil model, Advanced UltraHD model to forecast conversion of gases (O₃→NO₂, etc.) and generation, transport and sedimentation of dust or PM, several simulation scenarios. Other external data are required for model input and simulation, such as orography (land height), land use (urban, forest, agriculture etc.), albedo, and vegetation data (type, density, green fraction,...).

Within the data workflow, all these data will be classified into three groups: available data, derived data, and measured data, to clarify the data provenience and the status of anonymization, to define the level of openness, to check if the data are in line with the FAIR principles and if the required Metadata is complete, to store them accordingly in the repository or to provide licenses and to use this data in the CityCLIM Services, tools, and platforms.

Figure 1: CityCLIM Data Management Procedure.

CityCLIM will use some data produced by citizen science. With regards to possible personal data, the Consortium ensures that data on individuals are transmitted and used in a secure environment; that the use of the data complies with ethical and legal requirements (including signed informed consent and applicable data protection laws); and that the use of both existing and new data is agreed with the data owner/data provider. Data records containing personal data are managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

3.2 Who will be responsible for data management in the project?

Data management activities concern the whole project and need to be coordinated and monitored at project and work package levels. Data management is also linked to the publication of project results and thus dissemination activities. Therefore, the following roles and responsibilities can be identified:

3.2.1 Definition of Roles

Table 1: Tasks of responsible persons regarding data management in the CityCLIM project.

Role	Tasks
Project Data Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • developing the data management plan and policy in cooperation with the project management and the technical partners • coordinating and supporting the technical realization in the different WPs (data survey, data repositories, metadata catalogues) • monitoring data management activities (both collection and publication) and deadlines and sending reminders to WP data managers • providing support to WP data managers • writing the data management plan (D8.11, D8.12) • providing solutions for specific issues in accordance with project management
Workpackage Data Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the implementation of the data management policy in their respective WPs • monitoring data management activities and deadlines and sending reminders to partners • offering customized help and further guidance for filling out the WP data surveys • asking partners for missing information or clarifications • providing input to the data management plan by analyzing and summarising the WP-specific data surveys • offering customized help and further guidance for publishing open data and open-source software • monitoring that open results (data and software) are deposited in the default repository or a complementary OpenAIRE-compliant repository and sending reminders to partners • monitoring that open results available in OpenAIRE are correctly linked with CityCLIM (see https://www.OpenAIRE.eu/participate/claim) • contacting the quality assurance and ethics committee in case of questions and ethical and privacy issues that may forbid a publication of the data

Role	Tasks
Dissemination Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> offering assistance in choosing the right publication path (green or gold open access) offering customized help and further guidance for publishing scientific publications ensuring that the open access policy of the journal complies with the H2020 open data requirements before the researcher submits a manuscript monitoring that green access (self-archiving) publications are deposited in repositories and sending reminders to partners monitoring that Metadata about publications is made available in the R&I Participant Portal (preferably automatically through OpenAIRE) and on the CityCLIM website monitoring that research data related to a publication is made available in repositories and linked to the respective publication monitoring possible embargo periods and sending reminders to partners monitoring that publications available in ZENODO are correctly linked with CityCLIM
Quality Assurance Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> performing quality assurance of open data before their publication keeping contact with data managers
Ethics Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> performing an ethics assessment of open data before their publication keeping contact with data managers and decide together with the ethical committee on critical issues
Data Provider / Scientist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> informing the data & dissemination managers when new open data/papers ready for publication are available describing the data (using appropriate Metadata) or scientific publication in accordance with the CityCLIM data management policy (e.g., according to the chosen metadata standard) and with the help of the tools (e.g., template, web form) provided by the project depositing (publishing into a repository) the data or scientific publication following the CityCLIM data management policy and with the help of the tools (e.g., catalog, repository) provided by the project

The responsibilities in CityCLIM were defined and the list is available within the Consortium in sharepoint.

4 Data Summary

4.1 Data summary at a primary state

This section is usually associated with detailed activities of the project. For the DMP at a primary stage of the research process (i.e., first six months of the research project), it should include main activities performed within Work Packages (WPs) and break them down to fit into a research data management lifecycle. A dataset description is required to describe different datasets or types of datasets that will be produced, derived, or reused during the project.

The following points should be considered:

Table 2: Points and questions and their explanation regarding data summary.

Points/Questions	Explanation
<i>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the project's objectives?</i>	Data collection is usually at the beginning stages of research data management lifecycles to set the background of what is needed (data generation), what is already there (data reuse), and how to best use it to fulfill the project's objectives (why).
<i>What types of data will the project generate/collect?/ Will you reuse any existing data and how?</i>	<p>The main distinction between data types is between primary data and secondary data. Data collection may contain both primary and secondary data depending on the source where they have been derived from. Primary data has been collected for the first time and has not undergone data processing and/or analysis yet. Secondary data is data that has been cleaned up, analyzed, and shared by others (published or unpublished), and they are those that are typically reused.</p> <p>The expected data types include but are not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Primary/Secondary – Integers – Booleans – Characters – Floating-point numbers – Alphanumeric strings – Other (to be specified)

Points/Questions	Explanation
What formats of data will the project generate/collect?	<p>Data may be found in different formats. Usually, outputs of specific instruments/ services/ tools where data are generated and/or processed have a default way of exposing their outputs following specific standards. The most common distinctions between formats are proprietary and nonproprietary formats.</p> <p>The expected data formats include but are not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ASCII text-formatted data (TXT) – CAD data (DWG) – Comma-separated values (CSV) – NetCDF – dBase (DBF) – eXtensible Mark-up Language (XML) – Tab-delimited file (TAB) – Geospatial open data based upon JavaScript Object Notation (GeoJSON) – Geo-referenced TIFF (TIF, TFW) – Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) – Keyhole Markup Language (KML) – MS Word (DOC/DOCX) – MS Excel (XLS/XLSX) – MS Access (MDB/ACCDB) – OpenDocument Spreadsheet (ODS) – Open Document Text (ODT) – Rich Text Format (RTF) – SPSS portable format (POR) – Other (to be specified)
What is the origin of the data?	It is essential to know the primary point where the data was generated or collected.
What is the expected size of the data (in Bytes)?	Provide measurable examples per type of output based on common practices in the field. These might be relevant to the volumes of data and how many bytes of storage they occupy, numbers of objects, files, rows, and columns.
To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	Data generated or reused in the project can be useful for several stakeholders and third parties. Think about the target audience of your research, but also about possible third parties which could further exploit this data even after the project ends. → Data Repository → ZENODO

4.2 Naming Convention

Descriptive file names are essential for organizing, sharing, and keeping track of data files. Therefore, a naming convention needs to be set- up in each project considering the essential project aspects. Best practices in file naming consider the following facts:

- Consistent naming of all files and documents
- File names should be short but descriptive (<25 characters)
- Special characters or spaces should be avoided
- Use capitals and underscores instead of periods or spaces or slashes
- Use date format ISO 8601: YYYYMMDD
- Version number is obligatory
- Describe naming convention in DMP

Table 2 lists the proposed naming conventions for documents and research data. As stated in the D9.1 Quality Assurance Plan, each document in CityCLIM should be identified with an appropriate ID equivalent to the document file name. We will follow a naming convention also for research data. However, the discussion process is still undergoing.

Table 3: Proposed CityCLIM naming convention.

Specifications	Naming Convention		Reference
Document	CityCLIM-ddmmyy- xxxxxxx_v000_yyy.aaa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CityCLIM – Project indicator, • ddmmyy – optional – day, month and year when the file was prepared or used (especially relevant for presentation material) • xxxxxxxx – Short name of the document like deliverable name/ number or report number if necessary (e.g. D1.1, D3.2, R2, etc.). • V01 – version of document. • yyy – optional: the name or organisation like “V002_ATB”. This will facilitate the integration of documents and help us to identify the latest file version, • aaa – file extension, e.g. » .docx » for Microsoft Word documents, etc. 	D9.1 Quality Assurance Plan
Research data	CityCLIM_WPx_X_xxxxxxx_ v0x_yyy.aaa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CityCLIM – Project indicator, • WPx- Work Package • Pilot site identification codes are as follows: K:Karlsruhe, V: Valencia; M: Macedonia, L: Luxembourg • xxxxxxxxxx – Short name of the data set (maximum 8 characters) • V0x – version of document. (e.g. V01) • yyy –the name or organisation to be responsible for the dataset • aaa – file extension 	Discussion is going on

4.3 Versioning

Data versioning related to different versions of data storage that were created or changed at specific times. In the case of research data, a new version of a dataset may be created when an existing dataset is reprocessed, corrected or appended with additional auxiliary data. Versioning allows to track changes associated with ‘dynamic’ data that is not static over time.

Unique versioning allows for repeatability in data processing, enables data comparisons, and prevents confusion. It is a prerequisite for FAIR data handling and increases the trustworthiness of all kind of data. Numbering of data versions is a relatively well established in praxis. A consistent version numbering scheme enables data users to: (a) track changes and availability of new versions, (b) track which version is the previous version and with which version data processing was done (c) allow tracking the differences of each version. Therefore, the CityCLIM naming convention requires the information on the version.

Zenodo provides DOI versioning of all datasets uploaded to their communities, which allows to edit and update the uploaded datasets after publishing. Therefore, it is also possible to cite specific versions of an upload and cite all versions of an upload.

4.4 Metadata provision

Figure 2 describes the required administrative Metadata for documents that needs to be provided for each dataset.

Figure 2: Required metadata information.

Aside from administrative Metadata, every technical dataset must include Metadata describing the technical quantities, measurement- and/or processing procedure, unities, and optionally, if known, confidence parameters such as standard deviation. As an example, the INSPIRE platform of the European Commission provides guidelines for metadata provision and technical implementation for spatial data [EC INSPIRE 2013]. Technical Metadata can be understood as part of data handling.

4.5 Data Handling and Management at a primary stage

To provide a first overview of expected data within CityCLIM, a questionnaire collecting the essential information of some exemplarily dataset was carried out by the responsible data managers.

Table 4: Information on datasets at a primary stage.

Dataset reference and name	
Description of dataset	<p><i>Please describe the dataset content</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Its parameters,</i> • <i>units</i> • <i>temporal and spatial resolution.</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?</i>
Data Owner	<i>Who is the data owner?</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Data collection may contain both primary and secondary data depending on the source where they have been derived from. Primary data is data that have been collected/modelled for the first time and have not undergone through data processing and/or analysis, yet. Secondary data is data that have been cleaned up, analysed and shared by others (published or unpublished) and they are those that are being typically reused.</i>
Data types	<i>The expected data types include but are not limited to: Integers, Booleans, Characters, Floating-point numbers, Alphanumeric strings, Others. Please specify...</i>
File formats	<i>Please specify the file format of the data. Examples are txt, csv, netcdf, Json, tiff, kml, xls/xlsx</i>

Dataset reference and name	
Description of dataset	<p>Please describe the dataset content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Its parameters, • units • temporal and spatial resolution.
Used Vocabularies	Does the dataset use standardized vocabularies? If yes, please specify which standard is used?
Reuse of existing data	Will you reuse any existing data (also auxiliary data) for processing and interpretation and how?
Data production methods	Please describe the data production method or cite a reference if possible? (Manual/Semiautomatic)
Used QA/QC methods	Do you use any quality assurance and quality control methods during the data processing?
Data storage (where, expected size)	Please describe the data utility (e.g. Servers, file systems, graph database management). Where are the data stored? What is the expected size of the data (in Bytes) for a Day/Month/Year?
Potential for reuse	Can this data provide an added value for others in the project and outside? Please describe?
Potential stakeholders	Data generated or reused in the project can be useful for a number of stakeholders and third parties. Think about the target audience of your research, but also about possible third parties who could further exploit this data even after the project ends. To whom might it be useful?
Usage rights	Are this data Open Access (open data) or restricted data (closed data)? If not, please explain the reason? Are there any access conditions (licence, permits,...)? Does the data needs to be anonymized?
Data retention	Data retention is the storing of information for a specified period. Please describe this for the data?
Curator	Who is responsible for that dataset?

4.6 Data Management Plan using OpenAIRE

CityCLIM will use a collaborative online tool that helps researchers plan their Research Data Management activities (<https://argos.openaire.eu>). OpenAIRE is a pan-European research information system, which provides services to find, store, link and analyse research output from all disciplines. OpenAIRE aims at promoting and implementing the directives of the EC and the European Research Council on the promotion and funding of science and research. OpenAIRE supports the Open Access Mandate and the Open Research Data Pilot developed as part of the Horizon 2020 projects.

As the default DMP tool, ARGOS offers DMP templates that match the demands and suggestions of the guidelines on data management in Horizon 2020. A DMP template for the CityCLIM project was created and will be filled out by the data managers during the project's lifetime.

4.7 Data Repository

All open scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying open datasets, should be uploaded to a repository. The discussion on what repository to select is still going on within the project partners.

One possibility is to use the multidisciplinary open research data repository **Zenodo** (<https://zenodo.org/>) to comply with the H2020 Open Access Mandate. Zenodo is a "catch-all" open research data repository to gather research data across various scientific disciplines. It is for non-military purposes only. The repository is hosted and managed by CERN, and all data deposited to Zenodo is stored securely in the CERN Data Centre's cloud infrastructure. This multidisciplinary repository accepts multiple data types, publications, and software and assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

5 General Provisions - FAIR Data Management

The project aims to maximize access to and reuse of research data generated by the CityCLIM project. Hence, CityCLIM will manage data in accordance with the principles of FAIR data management– see also section 3.1. At the same time, there are datasets, or parts of datasets, generated in this project that cannot be shared due to, e.g., protection of the privacy of voluntary participants. The rules for FAIR data management and their questions that need to be answered are described in the following sections according to EC (2016). All these questions are implemented in the OpenAire Tool to create a DMP.

The following points needs to be considered:

- Making data findable, including provisions for Metadata
- Making data openly accessible
- Making data interoperable
- Increase data reuse (through clarifying licences)
- Allocation of resources
- Ensuring Data security
- Considering ethical aspect
- Others

6 Data generated in the CityCLIM Project

In Figure 3 all data sources are listed, which are required as input data for the generic city climate platform. This data can be divided into available, measured, derived (and historical data) and include remote sensing and airborne data, in-situ meteorological data, model and simulation data, and other auxiliary data.

Figure 3: Data (green box) in the CityCLIM project according to proposal.

7 Ethics

7.1 Ethical Issues

Citizen science also raises ethical issues that should be addressed before projects begin and throughout the scientific investigation. Ethical issues include data quality and integrity, data sharing and intellectual property, conflicts of interest, and exploitation. The most important is all issues regarding collecting and handling personal data. Scientists and researchers must always adhere to a certain code of conduct when collecting data from people and should consider aspects such as protecting the rights of research participants, enhancing research validity, and maintaining scientific integrity. Also, legal structures are established and in place to manage Citizen Science data that regulate the evaluation and storage of data and their accessibility. There are also binding standards relating to the handling of data rights. Coordination and data information offices are set up as points of contact to offer guidance on handling data (copyright, administration, and use). Volunteers actively involved in scientific activities, for example, when collecting data, are covered by insurance through additional agreements. However, in many Citizen Science projects, aspects of copyright or intellectual property issues are not adequately considered.

All data collected from stakeholders in the project will be following applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well processed and handled securely and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection. Since we do not know the exact scope and nature of the data at the beginning of the CityCLIM project, the ethical issues are under consideration during the project's progress.

7.2 European and national regulations

Germany, Spain and Greece are members of the European Union, and all countries are subject to EU law. Therefore, the most important data protection regulation is EU Regulation 2016/679 (the GDPR). In addition, there are several legislations in every country. This Law regulates among others the rules for processing personal data, formalities to obtain consent to process personal data, special rules when processing personal data about children and special rules when processing personal data about employees. Sensitive data are personal data consisting of racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, biometric data, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation. This kind of data can only be processed if a condition for processing special category data is satisfied but are not relevant in the CityCLIM Project.

Some critical issues according to this GDPR are (GDPR, 2022):

All processing of personal data must comply with all six general data quality principles. Personal data must follow six principles:

- **lawfulness, fairness and transparency principle:** processed fairly, lawfully and transparently
- **purpose limitation principle:** collected for specific, explicit and legitimate purposes and not processed in a manner incompatible with those purposes
- **data minimization principle:** adequate, relevant and not excessive
- **accuracy principle:** accurate and, where necessary, up to date
- **storage limitation principle:** kept in an identifiable form for no longer than necessary
- **integrity and confidentiality principle:** kept secure

The processing of personal data must also satisfy at least one condition for processing personal data. These conditions are that the processing is: (a) carried out with the data subject's consent; (b) necessary for the performance of a contract with the data subject; (c) necessary for compliance with a legal obligation; (d) necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject; (e) necessary for the public interest or in the exercise of official authority; or (f) necessary for the controller's or recipient's legitimate interests, except where overridden by the interests of the data subject (DSGVO, 2022).

Table 5: Regulations in the partner countries (DLA Piper Intelligence (2022))

Country	Regulations
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • German Federal Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz, or BDSG): in Sections 1–44, the BDSG contains supplementary regulations on the GDPR putting data controllers' rights and responsibilities in more concrete terms. Sections 45–85 of the BDSG implement the provisions of EU Directive 2016/680. • In addition to the BDSG, each federal state has its federal data protection law. These state laws only affect public bodies. • Germany does not have one central Data Protection Authority but a number of different Authorities for each of the 16 German states (<i>Länder</i>) that are responsible for making sure that data protection laws and regulations are complied with. • German Federal Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information (<i>Bundesbeauftragte für Datenschutz und Informationsfreiheit</i> – 'BfDI') is the Data Protection Authority for telecommunication service providers and represents Germany in the European Data Protection Board. • Germany's Federal Government set up the Data Ethics Commission (Datenethikkommission) on July 18, 2018. It was given a one-year mandate to develop ethical benchmarks and guidelines and specific recommendations for action, aiming at protecting the individual, preserving social cohesion, and safeguarding and promoting prosperity in the information age.
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Spanish Data Protection and Digital Rights Act 3/2018 (the "Data Protection Act") helps implement the <i>GDPR</i> and creates a new digital charter of rights. • The Spanish Research Ethics Committee (Comité Español de Ética de la Investigación, EEI). Created by the Law of Science,32 under the Council for Science, Technology and Innovation Policy, as a collegiate body of an independent and consultative character, on matters related to professional ethics in scientific and technical research
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Greek Law 4624/2019 "on the Hellenic Data Protection Authority, the implementation of Regulation 2016/679 and the transposition of Directive 2016/680" (hereinafter the "Law") (Government Gazette A/137/29.08.2019) was enacted and entered into force in August 28, 2019. The law regulates the operation of the Hellenic Data Protection Authority, introduces GDPR supplementary rules and transposes the Law Enforcement Directive into Greek Law. • lead supervisory authority :Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDP)
Luxembourg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two Luxembourg Data Protection Laws of August 1, 2018 have been enacted to implement the GDPR: (1) The Law on the organization of the National Data Protection Commission (CNP) and the general data protection framework. It gives the framework for the CNPD's organization, composition, and powers under the GDPR and the applicable national law. (2) The law on the protection of individuals deals with the processing of personal data in criminal matters as well as regulates matters of national security. • Article L. 261-1(1) of the Labor Code provides specific regulations concerning employer workplace surveillance. • In addition, the amended Law of May 30, 2005 on data protection and electronic communications governs the protection of personal data in the field of telecommunications and electronic communications, implementing the Directive 2002/58/EC. • lead supervisory authority: Commission Nationale pour la Protection des Données (CNP)

Country	Regulations
Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The existing Data Protection Act 2000 (<i>Datenschutzgesetz 2000</i>) was amended by the Data Protection Amendment Act 2018 (<i>Datenschutz-Anpassungsgesetz 2018</i>) which constituted the first implementation of various regulations related to GDPR, and was intended to enter into force simultaneously with GDPR. The 'Data Protection Act' (<i>Datenschutzgesetz, DSG</i>) has considerably amended the Data Protection Act 2000. In addition to the GDPR, it is now the central piece of legislation in Austria regulating data privacy. The Privacy Deregulation Act 2018 (<i>Datenschutz-Deregulierungs-Gesetz 2018</i>) further amended the DSG. Further amendments were included in the General Data Protection Adjustment Act (<i>Materien-Datenschutz-Anpassungsgesetz 2018</i>) and the research-sector specific Data Protection Adjustment Act – Science and Research (<i>Datenschutz- Anpassungsgesetz 2018 – Wissenschaft und Forschung – WFDSAG 2018</i>)
Switzerland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Federal Act mainly regulates the processing of personal data on Data Protection of June 19, 1992 (DPA) and its ordinances, i.e., the Ordinance to the Federal Act on Data Protection (DPO) and the Ordinance on Data Protection Certification (ODPC). In addition, the processing of personal data is further restricted by provisions in other laws, mainly concerning the public sector and regulated markets. The revised DPA will still provide for certain deviations from the GDPR provisions, thus requiring specific "Swiss Add-Ons" in several areas.

The proposed work in CityCLIM will fully comply with the regulations set out in the GDPR. In addition, CityCLIM comply with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out. Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research. The ethical aspects impacting the CityCLIM project are described in detail in deliverable 10 Ethics Requirements and respond to the findings of the ethics review performed by the European Commission in the proposal evaluation phase. However, since this D10.1-3 is a confidential document, a summary of the ethics and privacy strategy is included in this document.

7.3 Ethical Measures in CityCLIM project

Following ethical measures are under discussion to be followed within the CityCLIM Project:

- The ethical guidelines are based on the vision of using science and technology to create a better society and are reviewed continuously to ensure they stay up to date with developments in society and the challenges of today. They generally fall into these categories: research ethics, business ethics, and ethics in interpersonal relationships (Hagendorff 2020)
- Citizen Science data collection follows the six principles mentioned above, lawfulness, fairness, and transparency principle, purpose limitation principle, data minimization principle, accuracy principle, storage limitation principle and integrity and confidentiality principle.
- All data collection activities (interviews, surveys, etc.) will be designed to maintain privacy. Personal data will not be requested unless this is absolutely necessary. Vulnerable groups like minors and individuals unable to freely provide an informed consent will be excluded.
- All project partners are obliged by European and national law (GDPR) to protect personal data. To ensure compliance with all applicable ethical and privacy requirements, the privacy strategy encompasses all data assurance activities that will be performed in the context of the CityCLIM project. Under no circumstance will the deliverables or processes compromise the individual right to privacy and satisfactory handling of personal data.
- All personal data will be collected only upon receiving informed consent from the participants, and any participant providing personal data can at any time withdraw their participation and related data from the project.
- The participants will be given an information letter and a consent form (on paper or electronically). The information letter will provide information about:

- a. type of the collected data
 - b. How the data will be collected (interview, automatic data collection, etc.)
 - c. What the data will be used for. The information letter will explain the purpose of the project and the expected results. It will also be explained that published information always will be anonymous, and that no personally identifiable information will be published in any way.
 - d. How the data collected will be handled. The information letter will explain that personal data will be treated in full confidentiality and will be registered and stored in a secure manner. The data will be de-identified before it is processed (name or other characteristics serving to identify a person will be replaced by a number, and the list of identifiers will be kept separate from the data).
 - e. Who will have access to the data. The information letter will state that a very limited number of scientists will handle data and that confidentiality will be regulated by legal agreements. The data will be de-identified before discussing and processing within the project.
 - f. The rights of the participants. The information letter will state that participation is voluntary and that participants have the right to see the data collected about them and that they can withdraw from the study at any time without any obligation to explain their reasons for doing so (contact information for such requests will be provided).
7. Informed consent is created in different languages and according to the data protection laws that each Citizen Science participant needs to sign.
 8. Before any publications (e.g., scientific papers, public deliverables) with the potential of containing personal data is released to the public, it will go through an ethics and privacy screening to ensure that all data included is anonymized, aggregated and/or analyzed in such a way as to ensure that none of the content can be traced back to an individual participant or respondent
 9. Data analysis (e.g. in evaluations) will be carried out on de-identified and anonymised data. At the end of the project, all personal data will be deleted, and the de-identified data will be anonymized entirely, meaning that the links to the lists of keys will be deleted.
 10. CityCLIM does not collect any sensitive personal data as defined by either Directive 95/46/EC or by Article 19 of the new EU DP Regulation (GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679). The only personally identifiable data collected will be kept to a minimum. Furthermore, citizen scientists' names will be de-identified, anonymized, and not included in project reports or deliverables.
 11. In CityCLIM we need to distinguish between data collected from people taking measurements, e.g., with a SenseBox, and data from people who are asked to assess subjective perception of heat with the help of an app. In the first case, only minimal data is collected. This includes contact details such as name, address, telephone number and e-mail. This data is only used for contact purposes and will be irreversibly deleted upon completion of the collaboration on the project.
 12. The course of sensor data will be processed and displayed following the EU and national regulations. The possible tools include that the GPS data are shown with a location offset or only sections of the temporal-local course.
 13. When using the app, users are asked for some important information (e.g. age group, health status, gender group, living environment (city, ...) The answers are anonymized, as the answer is given by selecting a certain group e.g. age 12-18, 18-30, 30-45, 45-60, 60-70, from 70. The answers can thus no longer be assigned to individual persons.

8 Overview of Datasets

The list of expected datasets in the following constitutes the first version of dataset descriptions, and we recognise that it will be developed and increased as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets remains unknown at this time, e.g., size of the datasets, potential reuse options, QA/QC methods etc. An updated version of this list will be provided based on the fully elaborated DMP at the end of the project.

Table 6: Examples of data generated within CityCLIM

No.	WP/ Region	Dataset reference and name	Main partners involved
1	2	<i>(Tentative) Simulation data of urban pilot area</i>	OHB
2	3	<i>UltraHD meteorological model output for target regions Karlsruhe, Luxemburg, Valencia and Thessalonik</i>	MTL
3	3	<i>SuperHD forecast boundary data from target areas Karlsruhe, Luxemburg, Valencia and Thessaloniki</i>	MTL
4	4	<i>In-situ sensor data from stationary and mobile weather stations</i>	UFZ
5	5	<i>Data processors for City Weather Model</i>	<i>University of Valencia and OHB</i>
6	6	<i>Meteorological time series from MTL-Stations (in pilot areas Karlsruhe, Luxemburg)</i>	MTL
7	6	<i>Heat warning dataset</i>	MTL
8	Karlsruhe	<i>Urban Green spaces in Karlsruhe</i>	Karlsruhe
9	Karlsruhe	<i>Urban trees in the city area of Karlsruhe</i>	Karlsruhe
10	Valencia	<i>Air quality and noise pollution</i>	Valencia

All datasets described in Table 6 above are described in detail in the following.

Table 7: Example 1- WP2.

WP or Region	WP2
Dataset reference and name	<i>(Tentative) Simulation data of urban pilot areas</i>
Description of dataset	<i>(Tentative) This dataset contains simulated changes to urban areas including land cover, vegetation, ground level elevation of the pilot cities and their resulting impact to urban heat effects.</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>(Tentative) Simulated changes to urban areas are produced by the administrative climate services (WP6) and the resulting impacts are deduced from model outputs.</i>
Data Owner	OHB
Primary/Secondary dataset	Secondary
Data types	<i>pictures</i>
File formats	<i>.tiff, .nc, .png,</i>
Used Vocabularies	No
Reuse of existing data	<i>Yes, satellite data</i>
Data production methods	<i>Regionalization, Interpolation and visualization</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Not specified</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	OHB
Potential for reuse	<i>Limited, product is restricted to pilot cities</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>Local and national authorities if applied to other areas</i>
Usage rights	<i>Needs to be checked</i>
Data retention	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Curator	<i>Ingo Schollmann</i>

Table 8: Example 2- WP3.

WP or Region	WP3
Dataset reference and name	<i>UltraHD meteorological model output for target regions Karlsruhe, Luxemburg, Valencia and Thessaloniki</i>
Description of dataset	<i>binary dataset on UltraHD grid of 2m Temperature in °K, 10m-Wind components in m/s, Dewpoint in °K, every 5 Minutes, resolution: 100m, lambert conformal conic projection</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Used as input dataset for city heat forecast engines</i>
Data Owner	<i>MTL</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>primary</i>
Data types	<i>Floating-point numbers</i>
File formats	<i>binary files</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>No</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>Measurements and satellite products via GCCP (DEM, land use, LAI, LST, temperature, dewpoint)</i>
Data production methods	<i>UltraHD GPU Model run, automatic</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Applied, but not specified</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>GCCP, approx. 4 GB per model run and pilot</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>Moderate, reprojection to e.g., WGS84 suggested</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>e.g. Local and national authorities, health care associations</i>
Usage rights	<i>Open access</i>
Data retention	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Curator	<i>Stefan Horn</i>

Table 9: Example 3- WP3.

WP or Region	WP3
Dataset reference and name	<i>SuperHD forecast boundary data from target areas Karlsruhe, Luxemburg, Valencia and Thessaloniki</i>
Description of dataset	<i>binary datasets of 2D and 3D fields from the operational SuperHD model by MTL, hourly temporal resolution, approx. 1km spatial resolution (27 parameters T,U,V,W,P,QV,QC...)</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Used as boundary conditions for the UltraHD GPU Model. Necessary for running the UltraHD Model and reanalysis of specific scenarios</i>
Data Owner	MTL
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Primary</i>
Data types	<i>Floating-point numbers</i>
File formats	<i>binary files</i>
Used Vocabularies	No
Reuse of existing data	<i>Not specified yet</i>
Data production methods	<i>SuperHD Model run, automatic</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Applied, but not specified</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>GCCP, approx. 25 GB per model run and pilot</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>Moderate, reprojection to e.g., WGS84 suggested</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>e.g. Local and national authorities, health care associations</i>
Usage rights	<i>Restricted, property of MTL</i>
Data retention	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Curator	<i>Stefan Horn, Janek Zimmer</i>

Table 10: Example 4- WP4.

WP or Region	<i>WP4 - Citizens Science Concepts for Urban Climate Monitoring</i>
Dataset reference and name	<i>In-situ sensor data from stationary and mobile weather stations</i>
Description of dataset	<i>in-situ measurement of urban climate variables carried out by mobile and stationary weather stations; Air temperature [°C], Air pressure [mbar], Relative humidity [%], GPS coordinates [longitude, latitude]. Adjustable temporal and spatial resolution Potential additional values: Sound level [dB], Particulate matter concentration [$\mu\text{g} / \text{m}^3$], Soil moisture [%], Soil temperature [°C]</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>The in-situ weather data sets are needed to calibrate the climate models and to monitor the personalised exposure of e.g. heat on test persons,</i>
Data Owner	<i>UFZ</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Raw primary data, quality controlled</i>
Data types	<i>Floating point numbers</i>
File formats	<i>csv and database</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>No</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>storage in an internal database, quality-assured and equipped with Metadata, availability for archiving and publication (Digital Object Identifier (DOI))</i>
Data production methods	<i>different weather stations (e.g. meteotracker (https://meteotracker.com/) and senseBoxes (https://sensebox.de/))</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Quality assurance by using the System for automated Quality Control (SaQC) https://git.ufz.de/rdm-software/saqc.</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>internal database, expected storage requirement is about 150MB per month.</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>important for forecasting, information in retrospect (e.g. annual averages), in-situ data sets of extreme heat events</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>Data can be useful for weather forecasting service providers, city planners, interested citizens</i>
Usage rights	<i>? (The data can be made available on request via the UFZ database).</i>
Data retention	<i>The data does not have an expiry date once it has been made available.</i>
Curator	<i>Felix Schmidt (felix.schmidt@ufz.de)</i>

Table 11: Example 5- WP5.

WP or Region	<i>WP5</i>
Dataset reference and name	<i>Data processors for City Weather Model</i>
Description of dataset	<p><i>Satellite Data</i> <i>*Land cover, Land surface temperature (K), Land surface emissivity, NDVI, LAI, Surface Soil Moisture)</i> <i>* temporal resolution:monthly data</i> <i>*spatial resolution: from 10 m (sentinel 2) to 1km (Sentinel 3, TERRA, AQUA)</i></p> <p><i>Airborne Data</i> <i>*land surface temperature and emissivity</i> <i>* temporal resolution: intensive field campaign in 2023</i> <i>*spatial resolution: lower than 10 m</i></p> <p><i>In situ Data</i> <i>*Air temperature, Relative Humidity, Surface temperature and emissivity</i> <i>* temporal resolution: simultaneously with field campaigns</i> <i>*spatial resolution: transects</i></p>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Provide data for assimilations into numerical weather prediction models</i>
Data Owner	<i>OHB-SYS, UVEG</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Primary</i>
Data types	<i>floating point and maps</i>
File formats	<i>Txt, tiff, kml, xls, csv</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>Remote sensing terminology</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>In algorithms for assessing atmospheric correction</i>
Data production methods	<p><i>For satellite and airborne data: digital image processing(automatic)</i></p> <p><i>For in situ data: Error theory, manual</i></p>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Yes, automatic in Satellite and airborne data, manual for in situ data</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>Servers, several TB during the project. We have to find together with all partners how to solve the problem of data storage.</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>Very high. Maps and in situ data obtained in the 4 pilots (Luxembourg, Region of Central Macedonia - Thessaloniki metropolitan Area, City of Valencia, City Karlsruhe) can be used for urban planning, for example.</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>Researchers, town planning departments, public and private aerospace organisations</i>
Usage rights	<i>Open data</i>
Data retention	<i>During the time necessary to carry out the processing of in situ, aircraft and satellite data.</i>
Curator	<i>University of Valencia and OHB</i>

Table 12: Example 6- WP6.

WP or Region	WP6
Dataset reference and name	<i>Meteorological time series from MTL-Stations (in pilot areas Karlsruhe, Luxemburg)</i>
Description of dataset	<i>Spacial stationary time series of meteorological parameters: 2m temperature (K), dewpoint (K), rel.humidity(%), pressure(hPa), in city Karlsruhe added by precipitation(mm)</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Used for model verification and for assimilation to improve initialization fields for SuperHD and UltraHD models and visualization via the City Climate Web Portal</i>
Data Owner	<i>Meteorologix (MTL)</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Primary</i>
Data types	<i>Floating-point numbers</i>
File formats	<i>csv</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>No</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>No</i>
Data production methods	<i>Measurement sites with meteorological stations</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Applied, but not specified</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>MTL, approx. 10Mbyte/Monat</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>High, the reliable measurement could be used for further analysis</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>Local Authorities</i>
Usage rights	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Data retention	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Curator	<i>Stefan Horn</i>

Table 13: Example 7- WP6.

WP or Region	WP6
Dataset reference and name	<i>Heat warning dataset</i>
Description of dataset	<i>This data set contains areas of the city where given warning thresholds will be exceeded in a certain forecast range (e.g. temperature above 35 °C during the next day)</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Output of the city heat forecast engine to communicate warnings to the city administration and citizen</i>
Data Owner	<i>Meteorologix</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Primary</i>
Data types	<i>Integer</i>
File formats	<i>geoTIFF</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>No</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>Yes, but not specified</i>
Data production methods	<i>The gridded output of the UltraHD forecast is analyzed for thresholds and reprojected to a more common projection (e.g., WGS84)</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Applied but not specified</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>Meteorologix</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>High, especially for warning tools</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>e.g., local and national authorities, health care associations</i>
Usage rights	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Data retention	<i>Not yet specified</i>
Curator	<i>Stefan Horn</i>

Table 14: Example 8- Pilot Region Karlsruhe.

WP or Region	<i>City pilot Karlsruhe</i>
Green spaces	<i>Urban Green spaces in Karlsruhe</i>
Description of dataset	<p><i>Urban Green spaces:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Position</i> • <i>Size</i> • <i>Vegetation</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Greening measures serve climate adaptation. Green spaces allow rainwater to infiltrate and evaporate, which cools the surrounding area. They serve as recreational, cooling, and flooding buffers. They improve the microclimatic conditions.</i>
Data Owner	<i>City of karlsruhe / Horticultural Office</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Primary Dataset</i>
Data types	<i>ORACLE Spatial</i>
File formats	<i>csv; xls/xlsx</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>No</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>Maintenance of public green areas</i>
Data production methods	<i>Photogrammetrically measured; semiautomatic</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Position deviations of several decimeters are possible.</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>Oracle database of the city of Karlsruhe</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>Low for others as number, size and location are determinants of microclimate impacts.</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>None, as the data describe the specific local situation.</i>
Usage rights	<i>City of Karlsruhe</i>
Data retention	<i>Continuous data storage with weekly updates.</i>
Curator	<i>Horticultural Office (gba@karlsruhe.de)</i>

Table 15: Example 9- Pilot Region Karlsruhe

WP or Region	<i>City pilot Karlsruhe</i>
Dataset reference and name	<i>Urban trees in the city area of Karlsruhe</i>
Description of dataset	<p><i>Urban trees in public areas.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of species</i> • <i>Position</i> • <i>Size</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>Trees have the potential to store climate-damaging CO2. Trees evaporate water through their leaves, which cools the environment. Trees are a valuable source of shade in hot weather and improve microclimatic conditions.</i>
Data Owner	<i>City of Karlsruhe / Horticultural Office</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Primary Dataset</i>
Data types	<i>ORACLE Spatial</i>
File formats	<i>csv; xls/xlsx</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>?</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>For the maintenance and replacement of public trees</i>
Data production methods	<i>Photogrammetrically measured; semiautomatic</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Position deviations of several decimeters are possible.</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>Oracle database of the city of Karlsruhe with more than 100,000 trees in public areas.</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>Low for others, since number, size, and area occupancy are critical for local effects on climate.</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>None, as data describes the specific local public tree population.</i>
Usage rights	<i>City of Karlsruhe</i>
Data retention	<i>Continuous data storage with weekly updates.</i>
Curator	<i>Horticultural Office (gba@karlsruhe.de)</i>

Table 16: Example 10- Pilot Region Valencia.

WP or Region	<i>Valencia City Council</i>
Dataset reference and name	<i>Air quality and noise pollution</i>
Description of dataset	<i>Air Quality: According to attached table Noise pollution: According to attached table</i>
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	<i>The purpose of the generation and collection of data is, on the one hand, to comply with the regulations, and on the other hand, to inform citizens and serve as a basis for improving the living conditions of citizens. Their relationship with the project is to be able to improve in the achievement of those objectives.</i>
Data Owner	<i>Valencia City Council ; Regional government; Port of Valencia</i>
Primary/Secondary dataset	<i>Both</i>
Data types	<i>Floating-point numbers, Alphanumeric Strings</i>
File formats	<i>CSV, JSON. REST API</i>
Used Vocabularies	<i>FIWARE Smartdatamodel-based</i>
Reuse of existing data	<i>Published in Opendata portal</i>
Data production methods	<i>Automatic</i>
Used QA/QC methods	<i>Yes, with the methods referenced in European and national standards to Air quality and noise pollution</i>
Data storage (where, expected size)	<i>Urban City Platform. ~MB</i>
Potential for reuse	<i>high potential for reuse</i>
Potential stakeholders	<i>General population, students, universities, citizen associations, researchers</i>
Usage rights	<i>Open Data</i>
Data retention	<i>No limit for now</i>
Curator	<i>Valencia City Council ; Regional government; Port of Valencia</i>

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